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Rice Breeding and Varietal Improvements in Turkey from 1990 To 2020

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Halil Sürek ⁽²⁾Gihwan Yi*

⁽¹⁾Production and Research Manager (Ph. D), Agrobest Group, Kemalpaşa O.S.B. Mah. Kazım Karabekir Cad. No: 61 Ulucak, 35735, Kemalpaşa-İzmir, Turkey ⁽²⁾Professor (Ph. D), Dept. of Farm management, College of Agriculture and Life Science, Kyungpook National University, Daegu, 41566, Korea.

Corresponding author: Gihwan Yi

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Abstract

Currently, approximately 900,000 tons of rice is produced annually in Turkey from a rice cultivation area of around 120,000 ha, which is equivalent to 28% of the rice growing area in the European Union. Since 1990, 63 rice varieties have been bred in Turkey and national rice production has increased 3.5-fold. Therefore, we reviewed the shifts in agronomic traits and the genetic resources used in rice varietal improvements in Turkey from 1990 to the present. We also compared the agronomic traits of Turkish-bred and Italian rice varieties. The shifts in agronomic traits in this period showed that the number of days to flowering decreased by about one day from S_1 (1990-2003) and S_2 (2004-2015) to S_3 (2016-present). Additionally, culm length decreased by 6 cm from S_1 to S_2 and S_3 , and 1000 grain weight decreased continuously from S_1 to S_3 to the current average value of 24.1 g. In contrast, the head rice ratio increased continuously from 59.8% in S_1 to 64.9% in S_3 . The rice sector in Turkey must overcome new challenges of market competition with Italian rice varieties; we found that three Italian rice varieties (Cameo, Ronaldo, and Luna CL) shared 25% of the 2016 rice market in Turkey. In addition, Turkish rice had longer maturation periods, shorter caryopsis, and lower head rice recovery relative to Italian varieties. Pedigree analysis of Turkish varieties also revealed that 62% had at least one Italian variety as a hybridization parent. We suggest that extensive use of Italian varieties in Turkish rice breeding programs may result in reduced genetic diversity; hence, low genetic diversity could be a critical constraint in future rice breeding in Turkey.

Key words: Rice, Variety, Pedigree, Agronomic traits, Turkey

INTRODUCTION

The documented history of rice in Turkey dates back to the 16th century at which time it was cultivated in Ottoman society. Specifically, rice cultivation began in the Anatolia region and spread to Edirne. At that time, most of the rice was consumed by wealthy people as a popular cuisine (Nesbitt et al., 2010). Currently, the rice cultivation area in Turkey extends to 120,000 ha, which is equivalent to 28% of the entire growing area of the European Union, and this area produces around 900,000 tons of rice every year. However, rice is not a staple crop in Turkey; rice production quantity is only 3.2% of barley and wheat, and consumption per capita is only 8 kg per year (FAO, 2018). The main rice production regions in Turkey are Marmara and the Black Sea area. Edirne, Balıkesir, Canakkale, Tekirdağ, and Bursa Provinces in Marmara produce 71% of Turkey's rice, while Samsun, Çorum, Sinop, and Kastamonu Province in the Black Sea region produces 24% (IPAD, 2016).

A rice research program was initiated in 1970 in Turkey. However, research activities were limited to solving regional problems until a legitimated breeding program began in 1982 with coordination from National Rice Research Projects (Sürek, 1997). The organization of rice breeding activities was primarily conducted at Thrace Agricultural Research Institute (TARI) in Edirne and at Black Sea Agricultural Research Institute in Samsun Province. In the 1980s, many rice germplasms were introduced to Turkey from other European countries as part of this research project. Four Italian rice varieties (namely Ribe, Rocca,

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Baldo, and Veneria), three Bulgarian varieties (Plovdiv, Rodina, and Ranbally), and one Russian variety (Krasnodarsky-424) were released in Turkey between 1983 and 1986. 'Baldo' variety was not registered in Turkey, however, it has grown under the production permit. The Italian varieties Rocca and Baldo were most widely spread across the country, whereas the Russian variety Krasnodarsk-424 was mainly cultivated in the Black Sea and Central Anatolia regions before Turkish rice varieties such as Osmancik-97 and Edirne disseminated (Sürek, 1997). By 1984, Italian rice varieties such as Bibe, Rocca, and others shared up to 84% of the total rice growing area in Turkey (Sürek, 2014). However, in 1960s Turkey, the average paddy yields of local varieties were around 3.5 tons ha⁻¹ (Sürek 2014).

Since Turkish rice varieties were first obtained in 1990 by pedigree breeding, 63 new varieties have been bred and registered to the present National Catalogue of Turkey (VRSCC, 2019). Due to advances in breeding technology and efforts to secure varietal improvements, rice yield in Turkey doubled from 4 tons ha⁻¹ in 1970 to 8 tons ha⁻¹ in the 2010s (FAO, 2018). Despite these improvements, the major constraints in rice farming in Turkey are cold temperatures experienced at the seedling & booting stage and rice diseases, especially rice blast caused by the plant-pathogenic fungus *Magnaporthe grisea* (Sürek and Gümüstekin, 1994). In addition, drought, water shortage, salinity (some coastal area), and high temperatures at flowering time, especially in south-eastern Turkey, are emerging limitations in rice farming. The rice breeding program in Turkey cogently focused on improving short stature with lodging resistance and cold tolerance, as well as achieving high yields (paddy and milled), early or medium-early maturation (120-140 days), and long and translucent caryopsis (Sürek, 1997).

Despite the relatively short history of rice breeding in Turkey, and rice not being a staple crop, substantial advances have been achieved in rice breeding and related research areas in the last 30 years. In previous research, varietal improvements and the contribution of breeding to rice productivity have been documented (Sürek, 1997, 2014). However, there is a lack of research on the shift in breeding schemes and the genetic materials used in breeding during this period. Therefore, we reviewed the genetic resources used in rice varietal improvements and the chronic shifts of agronomic traits in Turkey from 1990 to 2020. We also compared the agronomic traits of Turkish-bred rice with those of recently registered Italian rice varieties to evaluate market competencies.

RICE VARIETAL IMPROVEMENTS AND THE GENETIC BACKGROUND

The varietal improvements of rice in Turkey can be divided into three stages according to the parent origins of pedigree (Table 1). During the first stage (1990 to 2003), denoted S₁, 15 varieties were released: Italian, Bulgarian, and Russian varieties were used for hybridization, while the local variety Akçeltik was also used as a parent in the breeding of another variety, Meriç. In S₁, the most frequently used germplasms for genetic hybridization were the Italian varieties Baldo and Rocca.

In the second stage (2004-2015), denoted S₂, breeders began to use Turkish varieties or elite lines as parents for hybridization. Of the released varieties bred in this stage, 18 of 28 had one or two hybridization parents of Turkish origin. The fragrant rice Aromatik-1 and the black rice Siyah-1 were introduced from the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) and registered to the National Catalogue by TARI. One important event during S₂ was the release of two high-yielding varieties (Küplü and Manyas Yildizi) via hybridization between the *indica* elite line introduced from the IRRI and the Italian *japonica* rice varieties Veneria and Baldo.

The third stage (from 2017 until the present), denoted S₃, represents the age of Clearfield® in terms of herbicide resistance. For example, 10 of 20 rice varieties released in S₃ were imidazolinone resistant.

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Clearfield® technology has been widely adopted in the USA, Latin American countries, and Europe; it gives the advantage of selective red rice control through imidazolinone resistance, which has led to its rapid adoption by rice farmers (Sign et al., 2017). For example, since 2009, 34 Clearfield® rice varieties have been registered in the EU plant variety database. Moreover, in Italy, the Clearfield® rice growing area contributes 35% of the rice cultivation area (Hansjoerg, 2017). However, the occurrence of imidazolinone-resistant red rice (IMI-R) has recently been reported worldwide; thus, the future of Clearfield® remains unclear (Kalsing et al., 2019). Aside from IMI-R varieties, in S₃, 4 of the 10 non-IMI-R varieties registered were bred via an *indica* × *japonica* crossing. Indeed, the use of *indica* × *japonica* hybridization tended to increase in Turkish breeding since S₂.

In the last three decades, the major breeding targets have changed in line with farmers' requests and socio-environmental situations (Table 1). High yields and good grain quality were the major breeding targets in S₁. The varietal purpose was diversified in S₂ from yield capacity and grain quality to favorable plant architecture, disease resistance (especially to rice blast from *Prycularia oryzae*), milling properties, grain shape, caryopsis color, and fragrance of grain. In S₃, herbicide resistance was introduced for efficient control of red rice and weeds. Grain appearance characteristics, such as length, color, and transparency, and grain aroma were emphasized as breeding objectives in this third stage in line with market preferences. Previously, Turkey had experienced a blast epidemic that caused a 20% yield loss in the Trakya regions (Sürek and Beşer, 1997). Hence, around 16% of the current released varieties have blast resistance. Although rice blast can be controlled by efficient chemical spraying, it is suggested that resistance genes need to be introduced into future varieties to increase the sustainability of agricultural practices.

In Turkey, 76 rice varieties have been listed in the National Catalogue of the Variety Registration and Seed Certification Center (VRSCC) since 1990. The number of varieties registered annually increased sharply after 2013, and Italian varieties were registered in Turkey after 2015 (Fig. 1). Furthermore, 63 of the 76 national listed varieties were Turkish-bred, whereas 11 varieties that originated from Italy were registered by private companies (VRSCC, 2019). Two rice varieties, Aromatik-1 and Siyah-1, were introduced by the IRRI from the International Network for Genetic Evaluation of Rice program. Figure 2 shows the pedigree origin of 63 Turkish-bred rice varieties. In an analysis of these varieties, 11 (17%) had both Turkish varieties as hybridization parents, 16 (25%) were hybrids of Italian and Turkish varieties, 13 (21%) had both Italian varieties as hybridization parents, and 10 (16%) had an Italian variety as one parent. However, only 10 varieties (16%) were the result of a crossing of a Turkish variety with a variety of non-Turkish origin. The pedigree analysis also revealed that 39 (62%) Turkish varieties had at least one Italian variety as a hybridization parent; importantly, this result excludes the use of Italian germplasms for ancestral pedigrees in the breeding of Turkish varieties. Other varieties used in breeding programs included those from Bulgaria, Russia, and the Philippines. Nevertheless, the extensive use of Italian varieties may result in the deterioration of genetic diversity, and low genetic diversity could be a critical constraint in future rice breeding of Turkish varieties. Indeed, Cömertpay et al. (2015) found that 34 of 39 Turkish rice varieties belonged to two groups always with Italian varieties by combined analysis of simple-sequence repeats and inter-primer binding site (iPBS)-retrotransposons. Similar results were reported from Jacquard's analysis of inter simple-sequence repeat markers from 28 Turkish rice varieties (Törün and Sözen, 2018).

CHRONIC SHIFTS OF AGRONOMIC TRAITS

We also analyzed the chronic shifts in agronomic traits, including days to flowering, days to maturity, culm length, caryopsis length and length/width ratio, head rice ratio, 1000 grain weight, and paddy yields, from 1990 to the present (Fig. 3A–H). Days to flowering changed to a small extent from S₁ to S₃. The average days to flowering were 79.8, which was the same value of Italian varieties presently registered in Turkey

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(Fig. 3A). The average days to maturity also changed to a small extent from S_1 to S_3 . Turkish varieties matured about 4 days later than Italian varieties at 128 days, and the earliest maturing variety was Haziran (102 days) (Fig. 3B). Recently, Turkey has experienced cool and rainy spring seasons due to climate change; hence, sowing is often delayed because of difficulties in land preparation and rice planting. Thus, early maturation and cold tolerance might arise as crucial breeding goal factors in future breeding programs. From S_1 to S_2 and S_3 , culm length decreased by about 5cm which was the same value in those of Italian varieties (Fig. 3C). Seed length also decreased from 7 mm in S_1 to 6.5 mm in S_2 and S_3 , which was slightly shorter than the seeds of Italian varieties (Fig. 3D). Caryopsis length and width ratio did not change across periods, but current values were slightly lower than those from Italian varieties (Fig. 3E). However, 1000 grain weight of milled rice decreased continuously from 28.7 g in S_1 to 24.1 g in S_3 , which was about 1 g less than the equivalent value in Italian varieties (Fig. 3F). Both seed length and 1000 grain weights are important factors that decide market preference. For example, Turkish consumers prefer long and big grain Baldo type rice (Azabagaoglu and Gaytancioglu, 2009). The Head rice ratio increased continuously from 59.8% in S_1 to 64.9% in S_3 . However, the average head rice ratio value (62%) was lower than that of Italian varieties (68%) (Fig. 3G). Finally, average paddy yield (Fig. 3H) decreased from about 859 kg/10 an in S_1 to 759 kg/10 an in S_3 ; however, the current value was 78 kg higher than that of Italian varieties (680.7 kg/10 a).

Extensive work on rice varietal improvement and the progress in farming practices have improved rice farming in Turkey. As shown in Figure 4A-C, the rice growing area in Turkey expanded from 53,000 ha in S_1 to 115,000 ha in S_3 . Moreover, rice production increased 3.5-fold from 260,000 tons in S_1 to 920,000 tons in S_3 . Rice yield also dramatically increased nationwide in Turkey from 532 kg/10 an in S_1 to 798 kg/10 an in S_3 . As shown in Fig. 5A-B, national rice production and yields per unit area increased sharply after 2003. This increase coincides with the expanded growth area of the Osmancik-97 variety. Sürek (2014) reported that the growth of Osmancik-97 comprised 70%-80% of the total rice growing area in Turkey between 2005 and 2013, making it a leading variety in the country. Unfortunately, current data on the present growing area of Osmancik-97 was not available; nevertheless, it is suggested that the current increase in rice production in Turkey originates from the growth of Osmancik-97, which is a high-yield variety (8-10 tons ha⁻¹) with medium plant height, cold tolerance, and moderate tolerance to neck and panicle blast. Additionally, Osmancik-97 (Fig. 6) shows a good response to nitrogen fertilizer, good grain and cooking quality, and a high head rice yield (65%-70%).

CONCLUSION

In the past 30 years, there have been huge advances in rice varietal improvement in Turkey. The Turkish rice sector has great potential to make Turkey a major rice producer of the countries from the Eurasian region. Since 1990, 63 rice varieties have been bred by Turkish scientists and national rice production has risen 3.5-fold. However, the Turkish rice sector still has many constraints, including abiotic and biotic stresses, some of which originate from climate change. In addition, rice breeding in Turkey still has to compete with the work of multinational corporations. In recent years, at least eight Italian rice varieties have been disseminated for the first time in Turkey; indeed, Cameo, Ronaldo, and Luna CL shared 25% of the Turkish rice market in 2016. Although Turkish varieties have to upper hand on Italian varieties registered in Turkey in terms of performance in yield, Turkish rice has longer maturation periods, shorter caryopsis, and lower head rice recovery compared to the respective characteristics in Italian varieties. Another concerning constraint is the low genetic diversity of Turkish varieties, of which 62% have at least one Italian parent from hybridization (not including ancestral pedigrees of Turkish-bred varieties). In future Turkish rice breeding programs, broadening the genetic diversity of Turkish rice will be one of the most crucial factors for success.

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Table 1. Pedigree and major agronomic traits of 65 rice varieties bred in Turkey.

Variety	Year	Pedigree	Major traits
Ergene	1990	Delta × Zoria	EM
Altinyazi	1990	Baldo × Ribe	GQ
Meriç	1990	Delta × Akçeltik	GQ
Trakya	1990	Baldo × Komsomolsky	GQ, HY
Ipsala	1990	Rodina × Delta	GQ, HY
Serhat-92	1992	Rocca × Korasnodarsky-424	HY
Sürek-95	1995	Rocca × Rodina	HY
Osmancik-97	1997	Rocca × Europa	BL, HY, GQ
Kiral	2000	Gritna × Ballila-28	SPH, GQ

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Yavuz	2000	Rocca × 1979-70-1	HY
Demir	2000	Plovdiv × Lido	SPH, HY
Neğiş	2002	Vialone nano × Sequial	GQ
Gönen	2002	Bonni × Shinei	GQ
Kargi	2002	Baldo × Balilla	GQ, BL
Karadeniz	2003	Silla × Roma	GQ
Edirne	2004	Baldo × Calendal	GQ
Kirkpınar	2004	Ipsala × 80110-TR253-4-1-1	GQ
Halilbey	2004	Veneria × Ipsala	HY
Ece	2004	8203- TR413-6-1-1 × 8260- TR470-6-1-1	SPH, HY
Kizilirmak	2005	N1-41T-1T-0T × Yavuz	SPH, EM
Beşer	2006	Ipsala mutant	GQ, SPH
Şumnu	2006	Rialto × Korall	SPH, BL HY
Durağan	2007	Panda × Baldo	HY, GQ
Kiziltan	2007	Veneria × Thainato	SPH, HY
Gala	2009	Select from Osmancik-1	BL, HY, GQ
Tunca	2009	Rocca × Thianato	HY, GQ
Çakmak	2011	Trakya × N1-41T-1T-0T	SPH, HY, BL
Efe	2011	Baldo × Demir	HY, GQ, BL
Hamzadere	2011	Demir × 83013-TR631-4-1-2	HY, GQ, BL
Paşali	2011	Osmancik-97 × 82070-TR480-1-1-1-1	EM, GQ, SPH
Bafra Yildizi	2011	Ballilla-28 × TR666-8-1-1-1	SPH, HY
Mevlütbey	2012	Drago × Kiral	HY, GQ
Tosya Güneşi	2013	Savio × Baldo	EM, SPH
Manyas Yildizi	2013	IR66160-5-2-3-2 × Veneria	LTG, HHR
Biga İncisi	2013	Baldo × Korall	LLG, EM
Küplü	2013	Baldo × IR2557-3-1	SPH, GQ
Mis 2013	2013	YRF204 × Osmancik-97	AR, SPH, EM
Kale	2013	Demir × 82079-TR-489	SPH, HHR
Yatkin	2013	Sürek-95 × 82057-TR467-12-1	HY, HHR
Sürek M711	2013	Sürek-95 mutation	HY, HHR
Balaban	2015	Krasndarski-424 × Osmancik-97	HY, SPH, BL
Ülfet	2015	Baldo × Unknown from Russia	EM, HY
Sarhan	2015	Osmancik-97 × TR795	HY, HMR
Boyabatkalesi	2017	Gönen × Ariete	EM, GQ
Gemici	2017	Kirkpınar × Kiral	SPH, HY, LRG
IMI 2521 CL	2017	IMI (unknown) × Durağan	SPH, IMI-R
IMI 2554 CL	2017	IMI (unknown) × Halilbey	HY, IMI-R
Sur CL	2017	IMI (unknown) × Durağan	HY, IMI-R
Köprü CL	2017	IMI (unknown) × Ece	SPH, HY, LTG, IMI-R
Özgür CL	2017	IMI (unknown) × Edirne	LLG, IMI-R
Güneş CL	2017	IMI (unknown) × Edirne	LLG, IMI-R
Rekor CL	2017	Halilbey × IMI (unknown)	HY, GQ, BL, IMI-R
Asli	2018	Osmancik-97 × IR83260-1-1-1-5-B-3-1-2-B	HY, GQ, BL
Zybek	2018	Osmancik-97 × IR83260-1-1-1-5-B-3-1-2-B	SPH, HY
Bereket	2018	Halilbey × IR83260-1-1-1-5-B-3-1-2-B	SPH, EM, AR
Yildiz	2018	Osmancik-97 × Thainato	SPH, HY
Inci	2018	YRF-204 mutant	SPH, EM, AR
Turbo CL	2019	IMI (unknown) × Kiziltan	HY, SPH, HHY, IMI-R
Degirmen CL	2019	Osmancik-97 × IMI (unknown)	MPH, LG, IMI-R
Efsane CL	2019	IMI (unknown) × Ece	HY, LR, IMI-R
Aga	2019	Rocca × Kiziltan	SPH, LLG
Haziran	2019	Neğiş × Sandora	MPH, EEM, GQ

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Hasat	2019	Kiziltan × IR83260-1-1-1-7-1-2-B	MPH, HY, BL
Total		63 varieties	-

* Abbreviations: short plant height (SPH), medium plant height (MPH), early mature (EM), extreme early mature (EEM), blast tolerant (BL), high yielding (HY), good grain quality (GQ), aromatic rice (AR), long grain (LG), long & thin grain (LTG), long & large grain (LLR), high head rice ratio (HHR), high milling ratio (HMR), and imidazolinone resistant (IMI-R)

* The fragrant rice Aromatic-1 (2007) and colored rice Siyah-1 (2015) were introduced from the IRRI and registered by TARI.

Figure legends

Figure 1. Origins and number of rice varieties registered annually in the Variety Registration and Seed Certification Center (VRSCC), Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Republic of Turkey.

Figure 2. The origin countries of the hybridization parents of Turkish rice varieties released from 1990 to 2019.

Figure 3. Box plots showing decade shifts in the agronomic traits of Turkish rice varieties including days to flowering (A), days to maturity (B), culm length (C), caryopsis length (D), caryopsis length/width ratio (E), head rice ratio (F), 1000 grain weight (G), and paddy yields (H).

* Italian represents the mean value of Italian rice varieties registered in the Variety Registration and Seed Certification Center (VRSCC) in Turkey. The list of varieties (and their registration years) are Ronaldo, Nembo (2015), Cameo, Meco, Venere, Ermes (2016), Luna CL (2017), Vasco (2018), Furia CL, Barone CL, and Romeo (2019).

Figure 4. Box plots showing the decade shifts in rice cultivation area (A), paddy production (B), and paddy yield (C) from 1990 to 2018 in Turkey.

Figure 5. National rice production (A) and paddy yield (B) from 1990 to 2018 in Turkey.

Figure 6. Plant and grain appearance of the Osmansik-97 variety. Plant shape at the maturing stage (A), paddy rice (B), and milled rice (C).

Fig. 1.

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Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

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Fig. 4.

Fig. 5.

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Fig. 6.

